

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC - BEREUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- APRIL 2021
(RGN 23) ADJ 111 PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENT IN NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1HR

Instructions:

INSTRUCTIONS

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.*

Question One

- a. State eight (8) qualities of the Nurses - 4marks
- b. Identify the Five faculties of West Africa College of Nurses and their colours - 5marks
- c. State five functions of Ghana Registered Nurses/ Midwives Association - 5marks
- d. As a nurse on duty, how would you ensure the safety of the valuables and money of a patient who was rushed in as an emergency case - 6marks

Question Two.

Ethics

- a. Discuss **Five (5)** reasons why we study Ethics. - 5 marks
- b. State **Two (2)** Christian beliefs. - 2marks
- c. Give and discuss **Three (3)** beliefs in the Islamic religion. - 3marks

Law

- d. In 2012, Ghana passed a new Mental Health Act which aimed to create a new system of mental health care in Ghana. This Act has faced several implementation challenges.
 - i. Why is it important for Ghana to have a mental health law? - 8 marks
 - ii. Outline the **Two (2)** implementation challenges of the new mental health Act of Ghana - 2 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC - BEREUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- APRIL 2021
(PBM 4) ADJ 111 PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENT IN NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answers booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

QUESTION ONE

A 60 year old woman presents with iron deficiency anaemia. After investigation she is admitted for haemotransfusion. In the process of explaining the procedure to her, she tells you she is a Jehovah's Witness and so would not accept blood transfusion. Will you go ahead and give the blood to the patient?

- a. Give reasons for your action - 5 marks
- b. A 35 year old woman was referred to the OPD with a breast lump. Examination suggested that the swelling was malignant and malignant cells were confirmed on fine needle aspirate. The patient tells you that she does not want any treatment. What actions will you take as a nurse on duty. - 5 marks
- c. Nurses work with other professionals to provide total health care and so there is the need for collaboration. Explain the independent function (role) of the nurse - 3marks
- d. State five expectations from the nurse in receiving and making telephone calls on the ward - 7marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. Outline and discuss in your own words any **Five (5)** signs that indicate that a client needs spiritual care. - 5marks
- b. Discuss the **Two (2)** main factors that cause Human suffering according to Traditional African Religion - 2marks
- c. Mention any **Four (4)** signs of Spiritual Health. - 4marks
- d. Briefly explain the **Four (4)** Noble Truths which according to Gautama Buddha's Teachings are the causes and solutions to suffering. - 4marks
- e. Mention and discuss the **Five (5)** pillars of Islam. - 5marks

QUESTION THREE

Recently, there has been an increase in medico legal cases. As a result, the Ghana Registered Nurses and Midwives Association is organising a one day workshop for all newly posted nurses and midwives on medico-legal issues with emphasis on the tort law because this is where you would see many suits cases against medical professionals.

- a. Mention and explain **FIVE (5)** intentional torts that would be discussed during the workshop - 10 marks
- b. State the **FOUR (4)** objectives of the tort law - 4 marks
- c. What are the elements that are required for a patient to establish a successful case of battery against a nurse? - 4 marks
- d. Mention **TWO (2)** forms of patient abuse - 2 marks

HFNMTC- BEREKUM- CAMPUS
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER, 2018
(PBM2) PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENT
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

According to the International Council code of conducts, the responsibilities of the nurse/ midwives is fourfold.

- a. Explain the fourfold responsibilities of the nurse - 12 marks
- b. State the responsibilities of the nurse when witnessing a will - 4 marks
- c. State four (4) responsibilities and four (4) rights of the patient as contained in the patient's charter of the Ghana Health Service - 4 marks

Question Two

- a. The role and function of the nurse/midwife is threefold.
 - i. List the three roles and function of the nurse - 3 marks
 - ii. Explain each of the three roles and function of the nurse stated above. - 9 marks
- b. As a nurse on duty, how would you ensure the safety of the valuables and money of a patient who was rushed in for an emergency admission - 4 marks
- c. Explain any two ethical principles - 4 marks

Question Three

- a. What is Euthanasia? - 4 Marks
- b. Briefly explain four (4) arguments *for* and four (4) arguments *against* Euthanasia - 8 marks
- c. Briefly outline four (4) Jewish Beliefs - 4 Marks
- d. Briefly outline four (4) Islamic Beliefs - 4 Marks

Question Four

Asantekramo alias Kumah v. Attorney-General {1975} 1 GLR 319 is a medical negligence case that is reported in the Ghana Law Report. The case was heard before the high court in Kumasi. The facts of the Asantekramo case are essentially that in 1967, a 19 year old woman was diagnosed as having a ruptured ectopic pregnancy in a private clinic in Kumasi and was referred to the then Okomfo Anokye Hospital (now the Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital). The surgery was successful but the arm of the patient in which the intravenous line was set subsequently became gangrenous and infected and needed to be amputated. The 19 year old woman's hand was subsequently amputated. The family of the woman took the hospital to court. The witness in the case stated that when the intravenous fluid was insitu, the woman's hand got swollen and that backflow of blood into the given set was observed. Eight years after the incident the court gave judgment for the patient and awarded heavy damages against the hospital. That is, a successful action for negligence was brought against the hospital.

- a. Mention FIVE (5) commissions of an act that constitute medical negligence - 5 marks
- b. Mention FIVE (5) omissions of an act that constitute medical negligence - 5 marks
- c. List the five (5) responsibilities of the patient - 5 marks
- d. Briefly explain the circumstances that an abortion can be legal and illegal in Ghana- 5 marks

HFNMTC- BEREKUM- CAMPUS
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER, 2017
(PBM 1) PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENT
TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HR.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions:*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

According to the International Council code of conducts, the responsibilities of the nurse/ midwives is fourfold.

- a. Explain the fourfold responsibilities of the nurse - 12 marks
- b. State the responsibilities of the nurse when witnessing a will - 4 marks
- c. State four (4) responsibilities and four (4) rights of the patient as contained in the patient's charter of the Ghana Health Service - 4 marks

Question Two

- a. The role and function of the nurse/midwife is threefold
 - i. List the three roles and function of the nurse - 3 marks
 - ii. Explain each of the three roles and function of the nurse stated above. - 9 marks
- b. As a nurse on duty, how would you ensure the safety of the valuables and money of a patient who was rushed in for an emergency admission - 4 marks
- c. Explain any two ethical principles - 4 marks

ETHICS

Question Three

- a.
 - i. "I came to this Hospital yesterday in the night. I want to go home and die. The doctors and nurses do not care about me. Nobody seems to care about me" said the patient. What can you do as a nurse? - 5 marks
 - ii. I feel shy to disclose some secrets about my sickness to the Doctor. She will tell others about my case. What do you have to do as nursing students? - 5 marks
- b. Define the hospital chaplain with key terms? - 2 marks.
- c. In what two ways does one qualify to be employed as a hospital chaplain? - 2 marks.

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC - BEREUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- APRIL 2021
(RM 18) ADJ 111 PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENT IN NURSING / MIDWIFERY
TIME ALLOWED: 1 HR
ESSAY

Instructions:

- *Answer all questions*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet*
- *Each question carries 20 marks.*
- *Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks*

QUESTION ONE

The object of the Nursing and Midwifery Council is to secure in the public interest the highest standard training and practice of nursing and midwifery

- a. Mention **six (6)** functions of NMC, to help achieve the object - 6marks
- b. State **eight (8)** qualities of the nurse - 4marks
- c. Identify four (4) ethical principles - 2marks
- d. i. Mention the **four(4)** factors that influence contemporary nursing practice - 2marks
ii. State **six (6)** responsibilities of the patient - 6marks

QUESTION TWO.

- a. Name and discuss four (4) determinants of Ethics according to Fleet. Determinants of ethics according to Fleet: - 4 marks
- b. Mention **Six (6)** ways in which Spirituality can be improved. - 6marks

Medical negligence accounts for a significant number of medico legal cases in Ghana and negligence can take several forms.

- c. Outline the **FOUR (4)** elements that are required for a patient to establish a successful case of negligence against a nurse/midwife. - 4 marks
- ii. Falsification of records - 2 marks
- iv. False claims - 2 marks
- v. Fraud - 2 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC- BEREKUM/ST. MARY.S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER, 2018
RGN 21/ RM 16 (ADJ 111) PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENT
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HRS.

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
 - Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
 - Each question carries 20marks
 - Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

Nursing as a profession has evolved over the years and need to be distinguished from other kinds of occupation. Florence Nightingale who is described as the founder of modern nursing defined nursing as “the act of utilizing the environment of the patient to assist him in his recovery”. This definition has impacted very much on the development of nursing. Within the Ghanaian context, the Nursing and Midwifery council of Ghana is concerned with promotion of professional conduct and efficiency in nursing practice.

- a. Mention **EIGHT (8)** other duties/responsibilities of the Nursing and Midwifery council of Ghana - 8 marks
- b. Nightingale’s environmental theory linked health to five environmental factors. Mention **THREE (3)** of these factors - 3 marks

In 1966, Virginia Henderson’s definition of the unique function of the nurse was a major stepping stone in the emergence of nursing as a discipline separate from medicine. Henderson (1966) conceptualizes the nurse’s role as assisting sick or healthy individuals to gain independence in meeting 14 fundamental needs.

- c. Explain the definition of Nursing by Virginia Henderson - 4 marks
- d. Mention **five (5)** of the fourteen components of nursing activities or the 14 fundamental needs the nurse must assist the individual to meet according to Virginia Henderson - 5 marks

Question Two

Madam Shetu, was rushed to the emergency ward where you are working with head injury as a result of road traffic accident. She is confused and has no relative with her.

- a. How would you care for her property - 4 marks
- b. List four (4) faculties of the West African college of nurse and indicate the colour that represent each - 4 marks
- c. Explain the following terms as used in nursing ethics;
 - i. Autonomy - 3 marks
 - ii. Beneficence - 3 marks
- d. Explain three importance of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs to the nurse - 6marks

Question Three

- a. What is Euthanasia? - 4 Marks
- b. Briefly explain four (4) arguments *for* and four (4) arguments *against* Euthanasia - 8 marks
- c. Briefly outline four (4) Jewish Beliefs - 4 Marks
- d. Briefly outline four (4) Islamic Beliefs - 4 Marks

Question Four

Asantekramo alias Kumah v. Attorney-General {1975} 1 GLR 319 is a medical negligence case that is reported in the Ghana Law Report. The case was heard before the high court in Kumasi. The facts of the Asantekramo case are essentially that in 1967, a 19 year old woman was diagnosed as having a ruptured ectopic pregnancy in a private clinic in Kumasi and was referred to the then Okomfo Anokye Hospital (now the Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital). The surgery was successful but the arm of the patient in which the intravenous line was set subsequently became gangrenous and infected and needed to be amputated. The 19 year old woman's hand was subsequently amputated. The family of the woman took the hospital to court. The witness in the case stated that when the intravenous fluid was insitu, the woman's hand got swollen and that backflow of blood into the given set was observed. Eight years after the incident the court gave judgment for the patient and awarded heavy damages against the hospital. That is, a successful action for negligence was brought against the hospital.

- a. Mention FIVE (5) commissions of an act that constitute medical negligence - 5 marks
- b. Mention FIVE (5) omissions of an act that constitute medical negligence - 5 marks
- c. .List the five (5) responsibilities of the patient - 5 marks
- d. Briefly explain the circumstances that an abortion can be legal and illegal in Ghana- 5 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....

HFNMTC- BERKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS- DROBO

END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - DECEMBER, 2017

RGN 20 & RM 15 (ADJ 111) PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENTS IN NURSING/MIDWIFERY

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HR

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

- a. Define Nursing by Virginia Henderson - 2 marks
- b. Explain Virginia Henderson's definition of nursing - 4 marks
- c. Explain the following ethical principles
 - i. Beneficence - 2 marks
 - ii. Non maleficence - 2 marks
 - iii. Veracity - 2 marks
 - iv. Fidelity - 2 marks
- d. Explain three (3) importance of Maslow's Hierarchy of needs to the nurse - 6 marks

Question Two

Effective communications is a vital tool in rendering holistic care to patients in our various health care facilities and as such all nurses are expected to possess this important quality in order to render individualized comprehensive care to the patients.

- a. Outline **FOUR (4)** elements of communication - 2 marks
- b. Enumerate **FOUR (4)** conditions necessary for effective communication - 4 marks
- c. Mention **FOUR (4)** importance of communication - 4 marks
- d. State **FIVE (5)** importance of informed consent - 5 marks
- e. Nightingale's environmental theory linked health to five environmental factors. Mention **the five (5)** of these factors - 5 marks

Question Three

- a.
 - i. "I came to this Hospital yesterday in the night. I want to go home and die. The doctors and nurses do not care about me. Nobody seems to care about me" said the patient. What can you do as a nurse? - 5 marks
 - ii. I feel shy to disclose some secrets about my sickness to the Doctor. She will tell others about my case. What do you have to do as nursing students? - 5 marks
- b. Define the hospital chaplain with key terms? - 2 marks.
- c. In what two ways does one qualify to be employed as a hospital chaplain? - 2 marks.
- d. Mention four (4) roles played by the hospital chaplain. - 4 marks.
- e. Mention four (4) Sacraments. - 2 mark

NMTC- BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – DECEMBER 2016
D19 & RM 14:ADJ 111: PROFESSIONAL ADJUSTMENT
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

To ensure client satisfaction there is the need for quality improvement service

- | | | |
|---|---|---------|
| a. Explain four (4) dimensions of quality | - | 4marks |
| b. State six (6) barriers to quality assurance | - | 6marks |
| c. Outline four (4) effects of good quality health care | - | 4 marks |
| d. i. Identify four (4) ethical principles | - | 2marks |
| ii. Explain the four ethical principles stated above | - | 4marks |

Question Two

- | | | |
|---|---|---------|
| a. Outline six (6) functions of Nursing and Midwifery Council of Ghana (NMC) | - | 6marks |
| b. Mention four (4) qualities of a nurse | - | 4marks |
| c. Enumerate five (5) conditions necessary for effective communication | - | 5marks |
| d. As a nurse on duty, how would you ensure the safety of the valuables and money of a patient who was rushed in as an emergency case | - | 5 marks |

Question Three

- | | | |
|--|---|---------|
| a. Explain the following terms; | | |
| i. Abortion | - | 1 mark |
| ii. Chaplain | - | 1 mark |
| iii. Ethics | - | 1 mark |
| iv. Morals | - | 1 mark |
| b. Explain three roles and functions of the hospital chaplain | - | 3 marks |
| c. Identify any Three (3) of the religious sects and outline their belief about health and illness | - | 3 marks |

Question Four

- | | | |
|--|---|-----------|
| a. Explain the follow terminologies; | | |
| i. Defamation | - | 1 mark |
| ii. Liability | - | 1 mark |
| iii. Assault | - | 1 mark |
| iv. Bathery | - | 1 mark |
| v. The law of tort | - | 1 mark |
| b. State five (5) functions of the Mental Health Authority | - | 2 ½ Marks |
| d. State five (5) responsibilities of the patient that will help health care providers to offer quality service to the patient | - | 2 ½ Marks |

